

D4.2

Definition and specification of the operational scenarios

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
ITU	Intermodal Transport Unit
CMR	Convention des Marchandises par Route (Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road)
e-CMR	Electronic CMR (Convention des Marchandises par Route)
TOS	Terminal Operating System
ADR	Accord Dangereuses Route
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
ETP	Estimated Time for Pick Up
K-API	Application Programming Interface (API) developed by the KEYSTONE project
PCS	Port Community System
TMS	Transport Management System
API	Application Programming Interface
WOLF	Web Oriented Logistic Framework

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	8
2. Introduction.....	9
3. AS-IS / TO-BE methodology	9
3.1 Discover the project	10
3.2 Define AS-IS scenarios.....	11
3.2.1 AS-IS workshops.....	11
3.2.2 AS-IS Experience Map.....	12
3.3 Design TO-BE scenarios	13
3.3.1 TO-BE workshops	13
3.3.2 TO-BE Experience Map	14
4. Pilot 1 - Road transport digital ecosystem.....	15
4.1 Discover the project.....	15
4.2 AS-IS scenario.....	15
4.3 TO-BE scenario	22
5. Pilot 2 - Intermodal digital ecosystem.....	24
5.1 Discover the project.....	24
5.2 AS-IS scenario.....	24
5.3 TO-BE scenario	29
6. Deliver demonstration scenarios.....	33
6.1 Road transport digital ecosystem	33
6.2 Intermodal digital ecosystem	33
7. Extending the demonstration scenarios	33
7.1 ITS at the Port of La Spezia Port – The MERIDIAN project	34
7.2 DSRC-RT technology	34
8. Conclusions	35
References	36

List of Figures

Figure 1. Participatory design methodology	10
Figure 2. Examples of “AS-IS Scenario Itinerary” during in-person meetings.	12
Figure 3. The Experience Map to be filled during the AS-IS workshop	13
Figure 4. The Experience Map to be filled during the TO-BE workshop	14
Figure 5 Main steps of the itinerary of Pilot 1	16
Figure 6 Example of CMR document.....	18
Figure 7. AS-IS Experience Map for “Pilot 1 – Road transport digital ecosystem”	21
Figure 8. TO-BE Experience Map for “Pilot 1 – Road transport digital ecosystem”	23
Figure 9. Main steps of the itinerary of Pilot 2	25
Figure 10. AS-IS Experience Map for “Pilot 2 – Intermodal digital ecosystem”	29
Figure 11 TO-BE Experience Map for “Pilot 2 – Intermodal digital ecosystem”	32

1. Executive Summary

This document presents Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2) “Definition and specification of the operational scenarios.” D4.2 is the final output of T4.2, “Definition of the demonstration scenarios,” which is part of KEYSTONE WP4, “Piloting.” WP4 started at M17 and will end at M30.

D4.2 describes how the two demonstration scenarios of the KEYSTONE project have been set up. In both scenarios, the KEYSTONE solution supports enforcement authorities that need to optimise and make more efficient checks and inspections regarding transport activities.

The first demonstration scenario, namely “Road transport digital ecosystem”, focuses on how the port authority officer will enhance the management of the access of trucks heading to the port gate. By receiving the trucks' estimated arrival time (ETA) from the logistic operators, the Port will use the KEYSTONE Web App to alert the truck drivers about the traffic status at the port gate. At the same time, the truck driver can optimise her/his trip operations by receiving information about the traffic status at the port gate and/or by triggering the processing/updating of the ETA to be shared with the port authority.

The second demonstration scenario, namely “Intermodal digital ecosystem”, focuses on how the road police enforcer will optimise trucks' checks and inspections. By using the KEYSTONE Web App, the road police officer can be notified in advance (before stopping a vehicle) regarding trucks and drivers that present irregularities.

This document contains the description of:

- the methodology adopted to define the demonstration scenarios, see Sect. 3;
- the “Road transport digital ecosystem” scenario with a detailed analysis of current pain points and improvements enabled by the KEYSTONE solution, see Sect. 4;
- the “Intermodal digital ecosystem” scenario with a detailed analysis of current pain points and improvements enabled by the KEYSTONE solution, see Sect. 5;
- preliminary planning of the demonstration activities, see Sect. 6;
- potential future integration of the KEYSTONE solution with other technologies under development and testing in different initiatives resulting from preliminary discussions with the KEYSTONE stakeholders, see Sect. 7;
- final remarks and conclusions, see Sect. 8.

In conclusion, this report is expected to support:

- T4.3 (WP4) at creating a digital ecosystem in the operational fields, which will allow automatic data sharing among the stakeholders;
- T4.4 (WP4) at defining a digital environment for intermodal transport;
- T5.1 & T5.2 (WP5) at describing ad-hoc KPIs regarding the evaluation of the pilots and the impacts of the solutions proposed;
- T6.2 (WP6) at keeping stakeholders engaged about the progress of the project.

2. Introduction

The overarching goal of KEYSTONE is the development and conceptualisation of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system, which allows enforcement authorities to access data for compliance checks. To achieve this ambitious goal, KEYSTONE is tailoring a standardised digital solution for developing a seamless, interoperable, and intermodal digital transport ecosystem. From a technical perspective, the KEYSTONE consortium is (i) defining API standards for data and information sharing between operators and authorities, and (ii) developing a web app that will integrate multiple data sources.

To demonstrate and test the validity of the digital solution, two real-world pilots will be set up and here described, see D1.4 (Keystone, 2024). The use cases definition highlighted the need for seamless data exchange among stakeholders, including transport companies, enforcement authorities, and administrative bodies. This integration can be enabled by the interoperability of the IT systems involved in each scenario with the KEYSTONE solution through the standardisation of APIs and protocols. As regards the interaction with regulatory and administrative authorities, the KEYSTONE solution should facilitate efficient communication and data sharing with the authorities to streamline processes and minimise delays. It must also support compliance with regulatory requirements and documentation standards.

The data exchange and interoperability in these pilots' implementations are based on the API Reference Model explained in D2.1, which provides standardised APIs and interoperability guidelines to enable seamless integration and collaboration between different stakeholders and systems. The standardised APIs for data sharing between transport enforcement authorities and logistics operators will allow the enforcement authorities to access all the necessary data to check compliance with rules applied in the transport of goods and passengers.

Finally, the following two pilots will be set up.

- Pilot 1 - the road transport digital ecosystem: it will be focused on road transport with the creation of digital ecosystems involving shippers and carriers from the perspective of a freight forwarding agent.
- Pilot 2 - the intermodal digital ecosystem: it will include intermodal shipments which require a much more complex management field in terms of automatic data management.

The pilots could be potentially implemented in all the Europe, but to simplify their management and implementation, a clear geographical scope is defined through the definition of demonstration scenarios. The two demonstration scenarios must be highly diverse to prove the solution in different contexts, by involving different authorities and compliance checks processes.

3. AS-IS / TO-BE methodology

A specific methodology has been adopted to define the KEYSTONE demonstration scenarios. This methodology is based on the principles of participatory design (Schuler, 1993), which aims to actively involve selected stakeholders in the project to ensure the result meets their needs and expectations. This methodology was already successfully adopted in another European project such as Shif2Maas¹².

As shown in Figure 1, four steps guide the designing of the scenarios.

¹ Shif2Maas project: https://projects.shif2rail.org/s2r_ip4_n.aspx?p=s2r_SHIFT2MAAS

² Participatory methodology in Shif2Maas: https://www.ip4maas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/IP4M_D2.2_Demonstration-requirements-and-scenarios-C-REL_resubmitted-after-rejection.pdf

- **Discover the project.** In this phase, the aim and the objectives of the demonstration scenarios are clearly defined, highlighting the needs and expectations expressed by the stakeholders involved. Moreover, basic knowledge of the demonstration sites is acquired through the definition of a *High-level itinerary* (i.e., high-level description, goal of demonstration scenario, stakeholders and means of transport involved in the carriage, etc.).
- **Define AS-IS Scenarios.** The adoption of an iterative process based on templates and interviews allows for gathering relevant information from the involved stakeholders about the status of the demonstration scenarios selected. The adopted participatory approach is articulated as an iteration of (i) collaborative activities with selected stakeholders (i.e. online or in-presence AS-IS workshops) to collect information and (ii) post-workshop elaboration of the collected information to produce an AS-IS *experience map* which aims to define a clear picture of current scenarios. In this phase, problems and areas for potential improvement are highlighted.
- **Design TO-BE Scenarios.** This phase aims to ideate and build future scenarios to overcome the problems identified in the AS-IS scenarios. This is achieved through a participatory approach articulated into an iteration of (i) a set of collaborative activities with selected stakeholders (i.e. online or in-presence TO-BE workshops) to ideate and brainstorm new scenarios; (ii) post-workshop elaboration of the collected information to produce a *TO-BE experience map* drawing.
- **DELIVER demonstration scenarios.** In this phase, the demonstration scenarios are finalised and delivered as input to tasks T4.3 and T4.4, dealing with the execution of the pilots.

Figure 1. Participatory design methodology

The pilot leaders (CIM and Gruber Logistics) have been involved in all the activities related to the definition of demonstration scenarios. Partners of WP2 and WP3 and external stakeholders were also involved in specific activities of the participatory design.

The *High-level Itinerary*, the *AS-IS Experience Map* and the *TO-BE Experience Map* have been defined through three different templates, respectively described in Section 3.1, Section 3.2.2 and Section 3.3.2.

3.1 Discover the project

The goal of the first phase is to understand the scope and the objectives of the demonstration scenarios, acquire knowledge about the context, and define a *High-level Itinerary* compliant with all the requirements (i.e. road or intermodal transport ecosystem, geographical areas, involved authority...).

As T4.2 leader, Cefriel organised a series of meetings with CIM and Gruber Logistics, leaders respectively of Task 4.3 (Road transport digital ecosystem – pilot 1) and Task 4.4 (Intermodal digital ecosystem – pilot 2), to discuss all the possible scenarios that could effectively demonstrate the KEYSTONE solution during the pilot phase. In particular, the pilots should focus on demonstrating how the KEYSTONE solution, based on standardised APIs for data sharing between transport enforcement authorities and logistics operators, can enhance the compliance checks performed by authorities.

The *High-level template* used during this step includes the following information.

- **Title:** brief title identifying the high-level itinerary.
- **Overview:** general description of the demonstration scenarios reporting at high level the itinerary (origin, destination and main steps), the means of transport involved in the carriage, and the compliance checks.
- **Aim:** what the KEYSTONE solution is aimed at enabling and improving during the demonstration scenarios.
- **Compliance check:** which kind of controls are performed in the scenario and which authorities are involved.
- **Stakeholders:** all the actors and stakeholders involved in the itinerary.

At the end of this phase, two demonstration scenarios have been identified: one scenario for Pilot 1 (*road transport digital ecosystem*) and another one for Pilot 2 (*intermodal digital ecosystem*).

3.2 Define AS-IS scenarios

This phase describes the status (“AS-IS”) of the demonstration scenarios identified in the previous phase. Afterwards, all information (e.g., data exchanged among stakeholders, tools used, etc.) is collected into an *AS-IS experience map* (see Figure 3).

In this phase, the *high-level itinerary is further detailed by splitting the itinerary into its main steps*. A detailed description of the main actions, the data generated and shared, and the main pain points is provided for each step. The analysis of the AS-IS is mainly focused on the steps of the itinerary where the authorities perform the compliance checks and, in the phases, where relevant data for the authorities are generated and shared by other actors of the scenarios. Nevertheless, for the sake of completeness, all the phases of the itinerary are analysed and reported in the AS-IS experience map.

The collection of information is done through an iterative process of workshops with stakeholders and post-workshop elaboration processes. After each workshop, the information collected through the AS-IS template is processed and revised. A new iteration of workshops helps to validate and enrich the AS-IS information. At the end of the iterations, the result is a complete *AS-IS experience map*. This map represents the input for the subsequent phase, namely the design of the TO-BE scenarios. The main insights are related to the identification of the current pain points and areas of potential improvement.

3.2.1 AS-IS workshops

Each workshop aims to collect and describe all relevant (data sharing) processes that are currently (AS-IS) involved in the specific scenario. The workshop is a collaborative activity with selected stakeholders. In case of physical meetings, the *AS-IS experience map template* is hanging on a wall, and the stakeholders are invited to collaborate in filling it with their ideas and thoughts by using coloured sticky notes (as shown in Figure 2). In case of online meetings, a tool supporting brainstorming, synthesis and collaboration must be

used. KEYSTONE used the Miro³ tool, which provides the proper environment to perform the same collaboration activities realised in the physical meeting.

Figure 2. Examples of “AS-IS Scenario Itinerary” during in-person meetings.

3.2.2 AS-IS Experience Map

The *AS-IS Experience Map*, shown in Figure 3, is the template used to support the data collection during the workshop activities. In the *AS-IS Experience Map*, each column represents a step of the itinerary of the pilot (e.g., planning and departure, arrival at the terminal). Each step is characterised by (rows of the template):

- **Itinerary:** means of transport involved in the step.
- **Main Actors:** The main actors involved in the step.
- **Key Actions:** The main activities performed in the step (e.g., loading goods on a truck, compliance checks, etc.).
- **Doing:** a detailed description of those activities (both physical actions and data sharing/generation) that a specific actor performs.
- **Touchpoints:** digital or physical tools used to perform the required actions (e.g., laptop, mobile app, calendar).
- **Data:** data generated or shared during the step (e.g., data about drivers, goods, etc.).
- **Pain points:** weak points (e.g., lack of data sharing) that represent a challenge for the actors involved in the activities.
- **Opportunities:** possible solutions (e.g., API for sharing data) that can enhance/improve the experience.
- **Qualitative evaluation:** rating of the actors’ experience in the step and rating the current solution’s digital readiness.

³ <https://miro.com/it/>

Figure 3. The Experience Map to be filled during the AS-IS workshop

3.3 Design TO-BE scenarios

This phase takes as input the *AS-IS experience map* (see Figure 4) and the current pain points and areas of potential improvement highlighted in each step of the itinerary. KEYSTONE focused on the pain points regarding the authorities' activities (e.g., compliance checks).

The design of the TO-BE scenarios aims to ideate and brainstorm new ideas to solve the pain points and address the areas of improvement through the KEYSTONE solution. The KEYSTONE solution provides new digital touchpoints that the actors of the scenario will use in all the steps of the itinerary to simplify communication and data sharing between enforcement authorities and the entities operating in the logistics sector.

In particular, the KEYSTONE solution is composed of a set of standardised APIs (called K-API) and a web app for supporting and enhancing the job activities of both enforcement authorities (road police enforcers and port authorities) and truck drivers. The K-API aims to become a standard that several entities will use and thus standardise the transport system. The web app represents the digital tool that provides a user-friendly touchpoint to interact with data shared by K-APIs.

3.3.1 TO-BE workshops

Cefriel organised a set of TO-BE workshops to investigate and describe novel solutions (“TO-BE”) for overcoming the current (“AS-IS”) pain points. By using a *TO-BE experience map template*, relevant information has been collected to support the definition of (i) new data sharing experiences both for authorities

and freight operators, (ii) new touchpoints to access the information and (iii) an added value to the entire freight transport scenarios.

Each TO-BE workshop is a collaborative activity with selected stakeholders (pilot leaders, WP3 and WP2 members and external stakeholders) and, as for the AS-IS workshop, it could be organised as a physical meeting or as an on-line meeting. Then, the same approach used for the AS-IS workshop is adopted: the *TO-BE experience map template* is hanging on a wall (or shared using an online tool), and the stakeholders are invited to collaborate in filling it with their ideas and thoughts using coloured post it.

As for the definition of the AS-IS scenarios, after a set of iterations of TO-BE workshops and post-workshops elaboration, a final version of the *TO-BE experience map* is produced and delivered to the T4.3 and T4.4 leaders, who are responsible for the implementation of the designed demonstration scenarios.

3.3.2 TO-BE Experience Map

In the *TO-BE Experience Map* shown in Figure 4, the columns represent the same steps of the itinerary of the AS-IS scenarios. In this case, each step is characterised by (rows of the template):

- **Itinerary:** means of transport involved in the step.
- **Main Actors:** the main actor involved in the step.
- **Key Actions:** the main activities performed in the step (e.g. load of goods on truck, compliance checks, etc.).
- **Doing:** a detailed description of all the activities to be performed in the step with the reference to the actors involved in the activity.
- **Touchpoints:** points of contact or interaction used in the steps (e.g., laptop, mobile app, calendar).
- **K-API data:** list of data exchanged via the KEYSTONE API solution.
- **KEYSTONE added value:** improvements and benefits derived from the adoption of the KEYSTONE API solution and new scenarios.

Figure 4. The Experience Map to be filled during the TO-BE workshop

4. Pilot 1 - Road transport digital ecosystem

4.1 Discover the project

The goal of “Pilot 1 - Road transport digital ecosystem” is to demonstrate the implementation of the data sharing concept through API standardisation in a digital environment for road transport.

The definition of the demonstration scenarios starts from the work done in D1.4 where the “*Use Case 2: Monomodal Road Transportation with Port Interaction*” was defined. It refers to a monomodal transportation scenario predominantly utilising road transport for the shipment of goods. A container is transported from a manufacturing company to a port, where a shift to maritime transport occurs. Administrative authorities, such as port authorities, play a crucial role in overseeing operations, supported by systems like the Port Community System (PCS). The interaction with public entities and regulatory bodies adds complexity, necessitating efficient data sharing and communication protocols.

This preliminary Use Case is further detailed and deepened during a series of meetings held between Cefriel (T4.2 leader), Gruber Logistics (pilot leader), and the Port of La Spezia that, through the involvement of a stakeholder included in the KEYSTONE stakeholders’ register, has accepted to join the piloting activity actively.

After a careful assessment, all the stakeholders agreed to have a truck, managed by Gruber Logistics, transporting a container from a manufacturing company to the Port of La Spezia. The Port represents a (portual) authority that carries out specific controls on the truck, its transport, and its driver. The marine shipment is directed to an extra-EU country and the documents related to goods are managed according to the eCMR format.

The *High-level itinerary*, created according to the template described in Section 3.1, is the following:

- **Title:** Road Transport Experience Map
- **Overview:** the scenario focuses on road transportation, specifically the transportation of a container from northern Italy to the Port of La Spezia. A data exchange with the port authority is established for supporting/enhancing the access management of trucks heading to the port gate. At the terminal (beyond the port gate), the container is loaded on a ship for an extra-EU destination.
- **Aim:** KEYSTONE aims to support the port authority (Port of La Spezia) in managing the access of trucks that will cross the port gate to reach the terminal. Integrating the platforms used by Gruber Logistics and the Port of La Spezia logistics operations are facilitated.
- **Compliance check:** The authority involved in this scenario is the port authority of La Spezia, which performs compliance checks on trucks at the port entrance gate and manages the entrance of trucks at the port gate.
- **Stakeholders:**
 - Port of La Spezia authority;
 - Gruber Logistics office;
 - Gruber Logistics Truck Driver;
 - Terminal.

4.2 AS-IS scenario

Cefriel organised several AS-IS workshops between June and September 2024 with Gruber and Port of La Spezia. Each workshop focused on outlining the *High-level itinerary*, by splitting it into different steps, described by the main actions, the data generated and shared and the main pain points. The result of these iterations is the *AS-IS Experience Map* shown in Figure 7.

The itinerary involves a road transport from a manufacturing company in northern Italy to Port of La Spezia, where the container is loaded on a ship directed to an extra-EU country. Road transport could be operated directly by Gruber Logistics trucks or external transport providers (as in 70% of transports where Gruber Logistics acts as a transport operator). That does not have any impact on how the KEYSTONE solution will be demonstrated in the pilot since the TMS of Gruber Logistics manages all the data exchange with external providers.

The Port of La Spezia is a natural landing place that offers multiple advantages for sea and land transport. Thanks to its strategic geographical position in the Northern Tyrrhenian Sea, it is one of the most important merchant ports in the Mediterranean and one of the most strategic nodes within the TENT-T Core network, the central trans-European transport network, as the core port of the Scandinavia-Mediterranean Priority Corridor.

The itinerary has five main steps, listed below with the corresponding key actions and summarised in Figure 5.

1. Truck before departure. A manufacturing company orders a transport service to Gruber Logistics. The Gruber Logistics office plans the shipment of a container (also called ITU, Intermodal Transport Unit) and prepares all the required documents. The main actor in this step is the Gruber Logistics office.
2. Truck departure. The truck reaches the customer, and the container is loaded on the truck. The truck starts the trip toward the Port of La Spezia. The main actor in this step is the truck driver.
3. Truck in transit. The truck driver transports the ITU towards the Port of la Spezia. The main actor in this step is the truck driver.
4. Truck arrival at the Port. The truck arrives at the Port gate, where checks and controls are carried out to manage safety and traffic issues. The main actor in this step is the Port of La Spezia authority.
5. Truck arrival at the terminal. Once the truck passes through security, it reaches the terminal where the ITU is unloaded from the truck and loaded on the ship to be shipped to an extra-EU country. The main actor in this step is the Port of La Spezia terminal. We added this step for completeness, but it is out of scope for the KEYSTONE pilot.

Figure 5 Main steps of the itinerary of Pilot 1

Steps 3 and 4 are pivotal points of the itinerary. The port authority can alert the truck drivers and schedule their arrival at the port gate. In this manner, the port authority can avoid congestion at the port gate and carry out compliance checks more efficiently. During steps 1 and 2, relevant data are generated and shared by the stakeholders (GRUBER office and truck driver).

In the following paragraphs, the first four phases of the itinerary are described in terms of data generated and shared, touchpoints (digital or physical tools), pain points, and opportunities.

Step 1: Truck before departure

Data and touchpoints

A manufacturing company based in northern Italy orders a transport service to Gruber Logistics. As a road transport operator, the Gruber Logistics office plans the shipping of the container (ITU) and prepares the documents related to the container according to the CMR document. Gruber logistic office selects the trucks to be sent to the customer and books the shipment to the Port of La Spezia by sending the name of the truck driver selected to the Port. The trucks and drivers could be provided both by Gruber Logistics and other external transport providers.

The CMR (Convention relative au contrat de transport international de marchandises par route⁴) is an international document that regulates the transport of goods by road between countries adhering to the convention. This waybill contains key information necessary to ensure the proper performance of the carriage and to define the rights and responsibilities of the parties involved (an example of the document is displayed in Figure 6). The main data included in the CMR are about the sender, the receiver, the itinerary, the carrier, the place of taking over, the place of destination, the description of goods, and the Container ID. The CMR document is generated using various tools (e.g. Excel).

Here are the details of the data contained in the CMR documents:

- Place and date of compilation: date and place where the document is issued.
- Sender: name, address, and other contact information of the shipper of the goods.
- Addressee: the recipient's name, address, and other contact information.
- Conveyor: name and address of the transport company responsible for the delivery
- Place and date of collection of the goods: place and date on which the goods are collected by the carrier.
- Place of delivery: place where the goods are to be delivered.
- Description of the goods: detailed description of the goods, including type, nature, quantity, seals and weight.
- Packaging: specifications on the packaging of goods.
- Customs codes or accompanying documents: any numbers or documents required for passage through customs.
- Special transport instructions: special instructions required for transporting goods (e.g., maintaining a certain temperature).
- Declaration of value or insurance value: any declaration of the value of the goods or insurance coverage.
- Transportation cost and ancillary costs: transportation costs and other possible charges (such as taxes or customs fees).
- Signature of the sender and the carrier: signature of the sender and the carrier to confirm that the goods have been taken over

⁴ https://unece.org/DAM/trans/conventn/cmr_e.pdf

- Scheduled ETA. The initially estimated arrival time calculated at the start of the journey.
- Actual ETA. The most updated estimated arrival time calculated in real-time based on current conditions, such as traffic, weather, etc.
- Distance Remaining. The remaining distance to the destination, in kilometres or miles. This data helps to provide a more accurate updated ETA.
- Average Speed. The average speed maintained so far or projected for the remaining distance, which impacts the ETA calculation.
- Current Location. The vehicle's current location, usually given in GPS coordinates or as a point on a map.
- Delay Information. Any anticipated delays with reasons, such as traffic, road conditions, or unscheduled stops.
- Time Remaining. The estimated time left to reach the destination, often calculated in hours and minutes.
- Traffic Conditions. Information on current or anticipated traffic conditions along the route, such as jams or incidents that might affect the ETA.

Calculated based on factors like departure time, distance, speed, and current traffic conditions, ETA is a critical metric for logistics, enabling planning, minimising waiting times, and coordinating resources at delivery points. In this phase of the journey, the ETA generated by Gruber Logistics is static data generated only according to the departure time. This static ETA information, enriched with the container ID, is stored in the Gruber Logistics TMS and it is shared only with the port terminal (the Port Authority does not receive the information).

Pain points and opportunities

The main pain point is that the Gruber Logistics office does not send the ETA to the Port Authority. The Port Authority could benefit from this information by enhancing the planning and coordination of the activities at the port gate.

Step 3: Truck in transit

Data and touchpoints

The container is carried to the port terminal by the truck. In case of disruption, the truck driver notifies the Gruber Logistics office about the delay by phone. Then, the Gruber Logistics office recomputes the ETA manually and emails the updated ETA to the port terminal.

In this phase of the journey, the port authority would like to manage the arrival of the trucks at the port gate to minimise the queue at the port gate. Nevertheless, the lack of information about the ETA does not allow to manage efficiently the traffic flow at the gate.

Pain points and opportunities

The main pain point of this step is the lack of a system to efficiently manage the sharing of ETA updates between the truck driver, the logistic operator and the port authority. On the one hand, sending notifications of delays due to disruption during the truck journey is slow, cumbersome and prone to errors. On the other hand, the port authority cannot send alert messages in case of queues at the Port to optimise the traffic flow at the port gate.

Monitoring and updating ETA is a key activity since it helps ensure timely arrivals, accommodate unforeseen delays, and optimise routes. This information should be made available to the port authority dynamically via digital systems.

Step 4: Truck arrival at the Port

Data and touchpoints

The truck arrives at the Port gate, where checks are carried out to manage safety and traffic issues. The Port Authority checks the validity of the badge of the truck driver and the container ID on the Port Community System (PCS). If all checks are passed, the Port authorises the driver and the container to access the Port area and to arrive at the Terminal. The driver informs the Gruber Logistics office via call about the completed check-in.

Pain points and opportunities

The main pain point of this phase is that long queues at the port gate may occur if the scheduling of trucks arrival is not properly managed. At peak times, the parking buffer area becomes saturated very quickly, testing the efficiency of the Port itself.

Since authorisation controls cannot be done in advance, the truck driver might be stopped at the Port gate because he/she does not have permission to get in, thus causing inefficiencies and slowdown.

The creation of a notice management platform could help the Port Authority manage and optimise the truck flow.

The qualitative evaluation section of the AS-IS Experience Map, shown in Figure 7, summarises the actual perceived experiences of all the actors involved in the scenarios and the digital readiness of the technical solutions currently adopted. Overall, digital readiness could be improved in almost all the steps of the itinerary. The main barriers are the lack of digitalisation and interoperability between the TMS of logistic operators and the PCS of Port Authority.

In conclusion, the main points of attention resulting from the analysis of the AS-IS scenario are:

- The lack of adequate management of ETA updates. ETA information is updated and shared manually, thus causing potential errors or delays in updates. Knowing the ETA in road transport can offer several significant advantages such as:
 - Improved scheduling and coordination: knowing the precise arrival time reduces idle time for personnel, improving operational efficiency;
 - Reduced operational costs: precise ETA tracking minimises fuel costs and vehicle wear by enabling route optimisation and avoiding congested routes;
 - Better risk management: real-time ETA updates allow transport managers to adjust for unexpected delays, such as traffic jams or weather changes, and proactively communicate with stakeholders.
- The lack of an integrated and digitalised system for sending alerts. Currently, truck drivers must use traditional systems (e.g. phone calls) to inform Gruber Logistics about delays occurring during the journey. This alert must be managed manually since the Gruber Logistics and Port systems are not integrated. This process is slow, cumbersome, and prone to errors.
- The lack of an advance notice management platform for port gate management. Currently, the Port Authority cannot notify trucks about possible delays at the port gate, since it does not have visibility of updated truck ETA and there is no integrated digital system to facilitate this communication. The benefit of such a solution could be twofold: the Port will receive predictive information on traffic levels, enabling timely corrective actions, while transport carriers will have access to detailed data on the authorisation status of goods and other logistical information, simplifying operations and reducing waiting times.
- CMR sharing is paper-based. CMR requires physical handling and management, so data cannot be sent in advance to anticipate compliance checks. The implementation of digital solutions like e-CMR could be an opportunity to streamline operations and facilitate the digitalisation of road transport.

Road Transport Experience Map

Overview

The scenario focuses on a road transportation, specifically the transportation of a container from northern Italy to the Port of La Spezia. A data exchange with the port authority is established for supporting/enhancing the access management of trucks heading to the port gate. At the terminal (beyond the port gate), the container is loaded on a ship for an extra-EU destination.

Aim

KEYSTONE aims to support the port authority (Port of La Spezia) on managing the access of trucks that are going to cross the port gate for reaching the terminal. By integrating the platforms used by Gruber Logistics and by the Port of La Spezia logistics operations are facilitated.

Compliance check

The authority involved in this scenario is the port authority of La Spezia, which performs the compliance checks on the trucks at the entrance gate of the port and manage the entrance of trucks at the port gate.

Stakeholder

- Gruber Logistics office
- Truck driver
- Port Terminal
- Port La Spezia authority

AS-IS Scenario Itinerary From North of Italy -> Port of La Spezia

Figure 7. AS-IS Experience Map for “Pilot 1 – Road transport digital ecosystem”

4.3 TO-BE scenario

Cefriel organised several iterative TO-BE workshops with Gruber and Port of La Spezia to analyse the pain points that emerged in the AS-IS scenario and envision the new scenario enhanced thanks to the KEYSTONE solution. The result of these iterations is displayed in the *TO-BE Experience Map* of Figure 8.

The TO-BE scenario focuses on optimising the sharing of documents and ETA updates between the actors during the journey to improve the port gate management of the port authority and the operational tasks of logistic actors. This will be achieved through the adoption of digitalised documents (e.g. e-CMR), the introduction of new tools (e.g. KEYSTONE web app for both port authority and truck driver) to simplify the sending and receiving of ETA updates and the sharing of information in a digital ecosystem (e.g. K-API). In the TO-BE scenario, sending the ETA information from the logistic operator to the port authority is pivotal. Nevertheless, how the ETA is generated and/or processed due to contextual issues is out of the scope of the project.

The following paragraphs describe how the steps of the itinerary will be implemented in the TO-BE scenario.

Step 1: Truck before departure

The shipment is planned and the e-CMR is shared on the K-APIs, from where it can be accessed by the Port Authority. The e-CMR is an electronic version of the consignment note used under the CMR Convention when transporting goods by road. It is used both as proof of delivery and as a contract of carriage between the carrier, the shipper, and the freight forwarder. It is a formal document that facilitates the digitalisation of road transport. Technically, it is an XML file produced by verified providers (e.g. Accudire⁵) with a structure that is compliant with technical standards.

Step 2: Truck departure

The truck arrives at the customer, where the container is loaded on the truck. After the ITU has been loaded on the truck, the Gruber Logistics office generates the ETA of the container and shares it via K-API. At this stage, ETA information is static data generated by the Transport Management System (TMS) according to the planned truck departure time. The ETA information is linked to the container ID, which is also included in the e-CMR document. Then the Gruber Logistics driver starts the trip toward the Port of La Spezia.

Step 3: Truck in transit

During the journey to the Port of La Spezia, the truck driver notifies the Gruber Logistics office about possible disruptions and delays by using the KEYSTONE web app. The TMS of Gruber Logistics uses this notification to update ETA, which is shared via K-APIs afterwards. By receiving an updated ETA, the Port of La Spezia can elaborate on a new plan for accessing the port gate.

In the meantime, the Port Authority can inform the truck drivers approaching the Port about possible queues and delays at the port gate and can suggest a new ETA to optimise the check-in operations. The notification can be sent by the KEYSTONE web app, which provides the port authority with an intuitive interface through which to send messages to specific trucks. This notification is shared via K-API and made available to the interested actors (e.g., Gruber Logistic office).

This sharing of information helps the Port to optimise the management of truck arrival at the Port and consequently helps the truck driver who can experience a smooth and optimised check-in process at the port gate.

Step 4: Truck arrival at the Port

The truck arrives at the port gate, and the Port Authority carries out check-in operations. These controls are facilitated and speeded up by the information about the eCMR shared in advance on the K-APIs.

⁵ <https://accudire.eu/>

In this step of the journey, optimising the scheduling of truck arrivals leads to better management of queues and parking areas.

Figure 8. TO-BE Experience Map for “Pilot 1 – Road transport digital ecosystem”

5. Pilot 2 - Intermodal digital ecosystem

5.1 Discover the project

The goal of “*Pilot 2 - Intermodal digital ecosystem*” is to demonstrate the implementation of the data sharing concept through API standardisation in a digital environment for intermodal transport. The complexity of the pilot lies in seamless data exchange and coordination across different modes of transport and authorities.

The definition of the demonstration scenarios starts from the work done in D1.4 “*Use Case 1: Multimodal Transportation with Intermodal Shipment*”. It refers to a multimodal transportation scenario involving the movement of goods utilising multiple modes of transport, specifically rail and road. The journey begins with an intermodal rail shipment originating from a port and transitioning to an inland terminal. Subsequently, the last-mile transportation operation is conducted via road, with enforcement authorities overseeing the process. Key stakeholders include private entities from the railway and road sectors and regulatory bodies like enforcement agencies.

This preliminary Use Case is further detailed and deepened during a series of meetings held between Cefriel (T4.2 leader), CIM (pilot leader) and Gruber Logistics. Gruber Logistics is involved in this pilot to ensure the connection with market freight flows as a freight forwarding agent.

After a careful assessment, all the stakeholders agreed on having rail-road transport from the Netherlands (Rotterdam terminal) to Italy (CIM Novara terminal). Finally, a roadside inspection on a truck is operated by the Italian road police enforcement.

The *High-level itinerary*, created according to the template described in Section 3.1, is the following.

- **Title:** Intermodal Transport (Rail & Road) Experience Map.
- **Overview:** the envisioned scenario involves goods departing from the Rotterdam intermodal hub, traveling by train to CIM Novara, and then being loaded onto a truck for their destination. During its road journey, the truck is stopped by the road police enforcer, who ensures compliance with regulations and the safety of the transport.
- **Aim:** the KEYSTONE solution aims to support the Italian road police enforcement by sharing crucial information in real-time. A more efficient check is ensured.
- **Compliance check:** the authority involved in this scenario is the road police enforcer. The truck is stopped for controls on the driver, goods and truck after it has left the CIM Novara terminal.
- **Stakeholders:**
 - Rotterdam terminal operator;
 - CIM Terminal operator;
 - road carrier operator;
 - truck driver;
 - road police enforcer.

5.2 AS-IS scenario

Cefriel organised several AS-IS workshops between June and September 2024 with CIM and Gruber Logistics. Each workshop focused on outlining the *High-level itinerary* by splitting it into different steps, described by the main actions, the data generated and shared and the main pain points. The outcome of these iterations is the *AS-IS Experience Map* shown in Figure 10.

The itinerary involves a multimodal transport (train + truck) from the Rotterdam intermodal hub to a destination in the north of Italy, passing through the CIM Intermodal terminal in Novara (Italy). The itinerary defined includes all the steps where data relevant to compliance checks are generated and shared.

The itinerary has 5 main steps, shown in Figure 9 and listed below with the corresponding key actions.

1. Train planning and departure. The itinerary starts at the Rotterdam intermodal hub, where the ITU (Intermodal Transport Unit) or container is prepared and loaded on a train directed to CIM Terminal in Novara (Italy). The main actor in this step is the Rotterdam Terminal operator.
2. Truck planning and departure. Meanwhile, the road carrier operator is arranging the truck transportation part for this intermodal carriage. The road carrier office books the trip for the ITU pick-up at the CIM freight terminal. Finally, an authorised truck driver departs to reach the CIM terminal. The main actor in this step is the road carrier operator.
3. Train and truck arrival at freight terminal. The train arrives at the CIM terminal and the ITU is unloaded from the train. Meanwhile, the truck arrives and checks in at the CIM terminal. Finally, the ITU is loaded on the truck. The main actor in this step is the CIM Terminal Operator.
4. Truck departure from freight terminal. The truck checks out and leaves the CIM terminal. The main actor in this step is the truck driver.
5. Truck in transit to destination. While the truck is on the road, it is stopped by the road police enforcer for compliance checks. The main actor in this step is the Road Police enforcer.

Figure 9. Main steps of the itinerary of Pilot 2

Step number 5 is the pivotal point of the itinerary, where the truck is stopped at a control point, and the road police enforcer checks it. During the previous steps of the journey, data required for carrying out and optimising the compliance checks are generated and shared by different actors (e.g. CIM terminal, road carrier operator and truck drivers, etc.).

In the following paragraphs, for the sake of completeness, all the phases of the itinerary are described in terms of data generated and shared, touchpoints (digital or physical tools), pain points and opportunities. Pain points and opportunities are collected for all the actors involved in the scenarios, both enforcement authorities and transport operators, to draw a more comprehensive description of the scenarios.

Step 1: Train planning and departure

Data and touchpoints

The Rotterdam Terminal informs CIM Terminal about the departure of the train (and ITU) via EDIGES⁶. EDIGES is the data interchange system of HUPAC, part of its Terminal Operating System (TOS), which is

⁶ EDIGES: <https://www.hupac.com/IT/Integrazione-dati-con-EDIGES-3d7c5d00>

named WOLF⁷. The information shared is the train list (a list of all scheduled trains with goods), the train CMR, the train composition, the ITU list, the ADR (Accord Dangereuses Route) for dangerous goods, the train closing and departure time.

Another piece of information shared is the train's Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), which corresponds to the train list timetable. In case of disruption, an updated train ETA can be calculated using the GPS installed on the carriages or by an EDI communication sent by an intermediate station. The updated ETA is communicated via the EDIGES system.

Pain points and opportunities

The train ETA cannot be shared with 3rd parties because EDIGES is a closed system and it does not permit the sharing with external entities. In this specific scenario, data sharing occurs only between Rotterdam and CIM terminals. An opportunity that the KEYSTONE solution could enable could be the sharing of the real-time forecast data regarding the train's journey (e.g. updated ETA) to all the actors involved in the scenario (e.g. to the road carrier operator who performs the second part of the intermodal journey or the enforcement authorities who do compliance checks).

Step 2: Truck planning and departure

Data and touchpoints

The road carrier office selects an authorised driver for the pick-up. The data of the trucks (licence plate and company) are associated with the chosen driver. The road carrier office books the ITU pick-up via the EDIGES platform by inserting the driver's authorised data (name, surname and truck data).

Pain points and opportunities

The truck driver cannot access updated train ETA information, especially in case of delay or disruption. The KEYSTONE solution could provide an opportunity to share the updated ETA information with all the actors of the scenarios so that the driver can better plan and optimise the arrival at the CIM terminal.

Step 3: Train and truck arrival at the freight terminal

Data and touchpoints

When the truck arrives at the CIM terminal, an OCR portal installed at the entrance automatically verifies the truck (license plate, vehicle integrity, shape...). Then, an operator of the CIM terminal manually checks the driver's data (authorisation of working for the declared logistic company, the truck being sealed and packed, etc.) using an Excel file or email. The truck arrival time at the CIM terminal is also registered.

At this stage, other data are generated, namely the train actual arrival time, the ITU unloading and loading status, the ETP (Estimated Time for Pick Up) and the ITU pick-up. This data is shared on the EDIGES system.

Pain points and opportunities

The lack of real-time updates on loading and unloading operations is a pain point for the authorities since this information could be useful for real-time tracking of the goods' movements.

A pain point for CIM is that the TOS EDIGES is integrated with the customer's system, but only a few customers have digital documents to provide. For this reason, the TOS cannot be leveraged to its maximum potential. In general, an opportunity that the KEYSTONE solution could bring is the standardisation of the data model so that all the information could be made available and accessible for all customers.

⁷ WOLF: <https://www.hupac.com/EN/WOLF-platform-9d39b000>

Step 4: Truck departure from freight terminal

Data and touchpoints

During the check-out process, two kinds of data are generated:

- the ITU pick-up exit date/time: digital data generated by the OCR portal system installed at the exit gate;
- the ITU Gate-Out interchange: a physical document for the driver.

Once the truck has left the CIM terminal, the truck driver calls the road carrier office to update them about the successful loading of goods and the truck's departure from the CIM freight terminal.

Pain points and opportunities

The lack of information about when trucks leave the CIM terminal is a pain point for road police enforcers because real-time information about the location and status of trucks and goods could help plan roadside checks more efficiently. In addition, information about trucks' time of departure from the intermodal terminal can improve the estimation of traffic along the area's main roads.

A pain point for the road carrier offices is that they are not automatically notified when the truck leaves the freight terminal (the truck drivers manually call the offices to inform them about successful check-out).

Step 5: Truck in transit to destination

Data and touchpoints

During the roadside checks, the truck driver shares the required documents with the road police enforcer. Most of the documents are on paper. The data shared in this phase are truck data (e.g., truck registration), driver data (e.g., driver's licence) and ITU data. If additional information is required, the driver needs to call his/her company for verification. The road police enforcer accesses the enforcement authorities' systems to check the data on the truck and driver.

Pain points and opportunities

The check of paper documents requires a lot of time and different systems should be accessed and queried by the police to check all the information. A solution that integrates and shares on a unique digital ecosystem all the digitalised information and provides a unique entry point to different systems could help authorities save time and optimise the controls.

Another aspect that could help speed up the checks could be the possibility of controlling the truck without stopping it, by accessing all the required information remotely. In this way, the road police enforcer could focus the checks on trucks, which would likely be illegal.

The availability of more accurate information about the time of transit of trucks on the roads could help improve the forecast of the flow of trucks on the road to set up checkpoints better.

Regarding the road carrier operator, most of the pain points are related to the lack of digitalisation of most of the information: drivers must manage a lot of paper documents, and they may have to call their company's offices to request missing information. A solution that integrates and shares all the digitalised information in a unique digital ecosystem could be helpful.

The qualitative evaluation section of the *AS-IS Experience Map*, shown in Figure 10, summarises the actual perceived experiences of all the actors involved in the scenarios. The role of road carrier is exemplified by the Gruber Logistic office. Nevertheless, the journey described in this analysis is valid and applicable to any road carrier operator. The *AS-IS Experience Map* shows the digital readiness of the technical solutions currently adopted. Overall, digital readiness could be improved in almost all the steps of the itinerary. The main barriers are the lack of digitalisation in some processes and the interoperability between the various data sources and repositories of the different actors in the scenarios.

The road police enforcer experience is quite low because some checks are still paper-based and several digital tools are not interoperable. In addition, the road police enforcer could take advantage of the sharing of data generated by other actors of the scenarios in terms of higher efficiency of the compliance checks (tracking of specific goods, better setup up of checkpoints, forecast of the flow of traffic on the roads, etc..).

In conclusion, the main points of attention resulting from the analysis of the AS-IS scenario are:

- The lack of interoperability between platforms of different actors. The information is stored in closed systems (TMS of the road carrier, TOS of CIM, systems of road police enforcer) and not shared with external actors. The implementation of a shared APIs ecosystem could help both authorities and transport operators optimise logistic management and controls.
- Lack of shared data about the ITU journey. Data about the ITU journey from origin to destination are currently not traced and shared with all the interested actors. Continuous real-time updates of truck locations, journeys and ETAs could provide useful information to support proactive management and enforcement.
- Multiple digital systems to retrieve information. Enforcement authorities need to connect to different systems to check or retrieve all information. A single digital entry point could help them optimise the controls.
- The efficiency of roadside checks could be improved. Enforcement authorities do not have access to data about trucks approaching the road network (e.g. flow of trucks, forecast of trucks leaving rail terminal), and, therefore, they cannot plan efficient roadside checks. In addition, they cannot check trucks remotely to identify trucks with a high probability of non-compliance and to focus physical checks only on these trucks.

Figure 10. AS-IS Experience Map for “Pilot 2 – Intermodal digital ecosystem”

5.3 TO-BE scenario

Cefriel has organised several iterative TO-BE workshops with CIM, Gruber Logistics (as a potential road carrier operator), WP2 and WP3 partners to analyse the pain points that emerged in the AS-IS scenario and to envision the new scenario enhanced by the KEYSTONE solution. The result of these iterations is displayed in the *TO-BE Experience Map* of Figure 11. As for the *AS-IS Experience Map*, the role of the road carrier is exemplified by the Gruber Logistic office.

The TO-BE scenario focuses on optimising the management of compliance checks thanks to greater and real-time availability of information provided to the road police enforcer via K-API and the KEYSTONE Web App. The data made available via the KEYSTONE solution are mainly about (i) the tracing of the ITU and trucks' movements and (ii) the drivers and trucks' data (e.g. driver licenses, tachograph data, trucks ownership, inspections and insurance).

Data on trucks' movements are valuable to road police enforcers because they allow them to know the truck flows and plan more efficient roadside checks in advance. In this specific demonstration scenario, the trucks monitored are the ones interacting with the CIM terminal. In particular, they are about:

- trucks scheduled to reach the CIM terminal for loading/unloading operations of ITUs from/to the Rotterdam rail terminal;
- trucks that checked in at the CIM terminal and are waiting for loading/unloading operations;
- trucks exited the CIM terminal.

Regarding European data, the TO-BE scenarios aim to demonstrate by simulation the potential usage of MOVEHUB as a routing mechanism that provides the interconnection of various European platforms (i.e. RESPER, TACHONET, and ERRU) in conjunction with the KEYSTONE solution. MOVEHUB can be invoked to obtain information about the driver (e.g., driver's license, driver professional qualification certificate), the tachograph (driver tachograph data, driver traffic violation data), and the truck (e.g. truck owner data, truck inspection service data, truck insurance data). However, as described in KEYSTONE D3.1 "App design, architecture and development plan", the interaction with MOVEHUB will be emulated using a mock-up system. The MOVEHUB emulator will provide information emulating those that can be obtained from MOVEHUB⁸, by exposing REST services that can be invoked by a KEYSTONE connector.

This information can be used to perform automatic checks on the trucks under monitoring. Trucks with possible irregularities in the documentation are reported to the road police officer who can select the trucks to stop for the physical inspection. This could ensure faster and more efficient compliance checks.

The following paragraphs describe how the steps of the itinerary will be implemented in the TO-BE scenario.

Step 1: Train planning and departure

The ITU is loaded on a train departing from the Rotterdam terminal. The data about the train (timetable, train composition, train number, train closing and departure time) and the ITU (train CMR) are generated by the TOS and shared via K-API.

The Train Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) is also shared via K-API and it is quickly updated in case of disruption during the journey, providing a real-time forecast of the train journey. The availability of the forecast data about the arrival of the ITU to the Novara terminal via the K-API is very important for the enforcement authorities, which can plan all the necessary compliance checks in advance.

Step 2: Truck planning and departure

Data about the trucks scheduled to reach the CIM terminal are collected. Data about the booking of the ITU picked up by the road carrier office via the EDIGES platform are shared via K-APIs.

Step 3: Train and truck arrival at the freight terminal

Data about the trucks that arrived at the terminal are collected. When a truck arrives at the CIM terminal, the OCR portal installed at the entrance registers the arrival time. This information is shared via K-API and used to monitor trucks checked at the terminal.

Step 4: Truck departure from freight terminal

Data about the trucks that exited the CIM terminal are collected. When a truck passes through the terminal exit gate, the OCR portal system records the date/time and shares this information via K-API. This data allows the knowledge of when (and how many) trucks are entering the Italian national system of motorways. The ITU is loaded on the truck and the data about the pick-up (e.g., pick-up status and pick-up time and date) is shared via K-API.

⁸ The reader can refer to KEYSTONE D3.1 (Section 4.3) for further information on how the MOVEHUB emulator will be developed.

The road police enforcer can use this information to intercept trucks and set up roadside checkpoints in advance.

Step 5: Truck in transit to destination

As trucks leave the CIM terminal, the road police enforcer at the roadside checkpoint is consulting the KEYSTONE Web App to monitor the trucks' movements. The KEYSTONE Web App remotely checks the truck and driver moving in the area around the CIM terminal by invoking the MOVEHUB emulator. As described in D3.1 "App design, architecture and development plan", the emulator provides information on the driver (e.g., driver's license, driver professional qualification certificate), the tachograph (driver tachograph data, driver traffic violation data) and the truck (e.g. truck owner data, truck inspection service data, truck insurance data).

If any irregularities emerge from this automatic inspection, the KEYSTONE Web App marks the trucks as suspicious. At this point, the road police enforcer can decide to stop the suspicious trucks for a physical inspection.

During the roadside checks, the KEYSTONE Web App will allow the enforcers to see data shared on the K-API by intermodal hubs (e.g. CIM terminal) and the data about the driver and vehicle provided by the MOVEHUB emulator.

According to the intermodal scenario, the KEYSTONE solution allows the following advantages.

1. The opportunity to create a sort of boarding pass for the ITU, which traces all the movements of an ITU from the starting point to the destination. This boarding pass could increase the visibility of the goods' journey to all the actors of the ecosystem.
2. The enforcement authorities can optimise the management of compliance checks thanks to greater and real-time availability of information. This can improve the efficiency and can reduce costs for compliance checks.
3. The K-API represents a new touchpoint shared among all the ecosystem actors where all the necessary information is shared in a seamless, interoperable, safe, and secure way. This solution can enhance stakeholder collaboration and foster data and information sharing between enforcement authorities and logistic operators.

Intermodal Transport (Rail & Road) Experience Map

Overview

The envisioned scenario involves goods departing from the Rotterdam intermodal hub, traveling by train to CIM Novara, and then being loaded onto a truck for their destination. During its road journey, the truck is stopped from the road police enforcer that ensures compliance with regulations and the safety of the transport.

Aim

The KEYSTONE solution aims to support the Italian road police enforcement by sharing crucial information in real-time. A more efficient check is ensured.

Compliance check

The authority involved in this scenario is the road police enforcer. The truck is stopped for controls on driver, goods and truck after it has left the CIM Novara terminal.

Stakeholder

TO BE Scenario Itinerary From Rotterdam Terminal -> To various destinations

Figure 11 TO-BE Experience Map for “Pilot 2 – Intermodal digital ecosystem”

6. Deliver demonstration scenarios

Preliminary planning is provided here to support stakeholders in executing the demonstration scenarios. A detailed and updated plan will be provided in the deliverables D4.3 and D4.4.

6.1 Road transport digital ecosystem

This section contains some information regarding the operational execution of the “road” pilot.

- Starting date. The pilot will start in May 2025, and it will end in November 2025.
- Stakeholders involved. Several stakeholders will be involved: Gruber Logistics, Port of La Spezia, CIRCLE, and ACCUDIRE.
- Number of days of piloting. 5 days per module (a module is a pattern of transport missions; to be checked how many modules will be carried on).
- Number of trucks involved. The pilot will test 1 truck per day.

6.2 Intermodal digital ecosystem

This section contains some information regarding the operational execution of the “intermodal” pilot.

- Starting date. The piloting will start in Novara, Italy, at the CIM rail terminal on 01/05/2025 and will end on 31/07/2025.
- Stakeholders involved. Several stakeholders will be involved: a road carrier (probably Gruber Logistics or another carrier), the CIM terminal, and the Carabinieri arm as a public enforcement actor.
- Number of days of piloting. We will plan at least three tests per month with three different trucks. During the entire test period, we will manage trucks for 9 days.
- Number of trucks involved. Three trucks for each day for a total of 27 trucks in the entire period.
- Number of trains involved. The pilot will test at least one train for each truck. Minimum 27 trains for the period, trying to test not only the Rotterdam trains.

7. Extending the demonstration scenarios

The KEYSTONE project is developing and conceptualising a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system that allows enforcement authorities to access data for compliance checks. To achieve this ambitious goal, KEYSTONE is defining an API standard (WP2) for data and information sharing between operators and authorities.

Moreover, the collaboration with stakeholders managed by KEYSTONE WP6 has depicted potential future integration with other technologies under development and testing in different initiatives. The following sub-sections provide a short overview of two promising technologies discussed with the KEYSTONE stakeholders. Further discussions on the possibility of integrating the KEYSTONE solution with the data provided by these technologies will proceed with the activities of WP5 and WP6. The possible connection and integration of the KEYSTONE solution with the additional data would potentially expand the information that KEYSTONE could provide to the authorities. These ideas for extending the KEYSTONE demonstration scenarios will not be tested in KEYSTONE and should be considered as recommendations and suggestions for follow-up projects.

7.1 ITS at the Port of La Spezia Port – The MERIDIAN project

To meet truck drivers' needs and reduce waiting time at the port gate, the MERIDIAN project⁹ has developed a pilot test for managing truck entrances within the port of La Spezia, thanks to a faster data entry system integrated with the other platforms owned by the Port Authority.

For this reason, the Pilot Project in La Spezia has started implementing new functionalities since October 2022. These will give the Port Authority information about truck arrivals to better manage the activities for accessing the port and the terminal.

The system is fed by the OBUs (On Board Units) already installed on many trucks coming to the port of La Spezia. After the involvement of vehicles identified among the road haulage companies that frequently came to the port of La Spezia, the system has been tested to integrate with the ERP of road haulage companies. The system can release the ETA (updated every 10 minutes) for each truck equipped by the OBUs, allowing the Port Authority to receive in advance the needed information for:

- carry out the authorization checks (access permits and operating data) on the Port Community System in advance;
- manage potential congestion in advance in the parking area of the port gate, jointly with the cameras already installed.

A Truck Federative Platform has been also developed to host all the data about the missions of the trucks coming to the port of La Spezia, including data about the operational availability, customs authorizations, gate entrance permits, and dangerous goods authorizations.

For the KEYSTONE “Road transport digital ecosystem” pilot, the results of the MERIDIAN project represent additional data sources to be integrated, which would expand the amount of information that KEYSTONE could provide to the authorities.

7.2 DSRC-RT technology

The Dedicated Short Range Communication Real Time (DSRC-RT) technology aims to facilitate roadside checks of tachograph infringements. After appropriate authentication, the tachograph transmits vehicle and calibration data as well as information about potential breaches and malfunctions to the inspection officers' DSRC-RP device via a small antenna installed on the vehicle's windshield. However, the DSRC-RT module does not detect infringements themselves but supports enforcement authorities in executing targeted inspections based on concrete suspicions instead of picking out vehicles randomly based on secondary suspicions. Logistic operators and drivers also benefit from implementing DSRC-RP since those who comply with all active regulations can expect fewer unscheduled stops at the roadside, thereby improving schedule reliability and cost efficiency.

For the KEYSTONE “Intermodal digital ecosystem” pilot, this solution could represent a new data source providing certified data. The information provided by the DSRC-RT technology could be integrated into the KEYSTONE Web App and made available to the enforcement authorities, with the logistic data coming from TOS and OCR systems. To be compliant with EU Regulations, only the enforcement authorities will be able to check the data from the tachographs through proper authentication and authorization mechanisms.

Continental¹⁰ is one of the companies that has developed a tool based on the DSRC-RT technology in compliance with the law¹¹. The collaboration between Continental and KEYSTONE is ongoing: Continental is one of the stakeholders joining the KEYSTONE stakeholder registry (T6.2) and it will be involved in further discussion on how DSRC-RT could be integrated in future extension of the KEYSTONE solution.

⁹ <https://meridian-corridors.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.continental.com/en/press/press-releases/20211112-vdo-dsrc-rp/>

¹¹ <https://tachoscancontrol.com/en/aktualnosci/tachoscan-control-dsrc-module-more-effective-inspections/>

8. Conclusions

This document represents the Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2), “Definition and specification of the operational scenarios”. D4.2 is the final output of T4.2, “Definition of the demonstration scenarios” that is part of WP4, “Piloting”. WP4 started on M17 and will end at M30. The benefits of the KEYSTONE solutions, namely the API reference model (WP2) and the web app (WP3), will be demonstrated on the field (T4.3 and T4.4). D4.2 describes how the two demonstration scenarios have been set up.

In both scenarios, the KEYSTONE solution is aimed at supporting enforcement authorities that need to optimise and make more efficient checks and inspections regarding transport activities. The first demonstration scenario, namely “Road transport digital ecosystem”, is focused on road transport with the creation of a digital ecosystem involving shippers and carriers. In this pilot, the KEYSTONE solution is mainly targeted at the Port Authority of La Spezia, which needs to manage access to the gate of trucks heading to the Port. The second scenario, namely “Intermodal digital ecosystem”, includes intermodal shipments, which require a much more complex management field in terms of automatic data management. In this pilot, the KEYSTONE solution is mainly targeted to the Italian Road Enforcement which needs to stop and inspect trucks on the road more efficiently.

In the first pilot, namely “Road transport digital ecosystem”, the *port authority officer* (Port of La Spezia) will manage the access of trucks heading to the port gate. By receiving the estimated time of arrival (ETA) of the trucks from the logistic operator, the Port will use the KEYSTONE Web App to alert the truck drivers about the traffic status at the port gate. At the same time, the truck driver can optimise her/his trip operations by receiving information about the status of traffic at the port gate and/or by triggering the processing/updating of the ETA to be shared with the port authority.

Finally, in the second pilot, namely “Intermodal digital ecosystem,” the road police enforcer can optimise truck checks/inspections. By using the KEYSTONE Web App, the road police officer can be notified in advance (before stopping a vehicle) regarding trucks and drivers that present irregularities.

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